

Multipath Cancellation in the Time Domain

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Abstract—Multipath signals present problems in a variety of signal processing application. Spatial domain approaches are often used to minimize these unwanted signals. This paper explores a time domain approach that can effectively eliminate multipath signals. The key to this approach is the use of time-shift operators. These operators allow the problem to be inverted and the original signal to be recovered.

INTRODUCTION

Multipath signals often occur in sensing and communication applications. In the water these signals can and do reflect off the water-air and water-sediment boundaries. The reception of the direct path signal followed by a number of multipath signals can be a problem.

This paper investigates a method to coherently estimate the desired signal from the direct and multipath signals using a time domain approach. This approach effectively eliminates the multipath signals by using the Moore-Penrose inverse to construct the original signal using all of the measured time series data. An important part of this calculation is an accurate estimate of the time delays of the various direct and multipath signals. This estimate can be made from the data using the maximum likelihood method.

What differentiates this approach from other techniques is the extensive use of time-shift operators. These operators have a matrix representation that can advance or retard time series data by any amount. These matrices also have the property that they are fairly easy to invert.

THE TIME DOMAIN MODEL

The time domain model may be represented as a received time series vector, y , that is a mapping, D , of the original time series signal, s , plus noise.

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \vdots \\ y_m \end{pmatrix} = D \begin{pmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ \vdots \\ s_n \end{pmatrix} + noise \quad (1)$$

The mapping, D , is essentially a series of operators that time shift the original signal. This can be conveniently written as

$$D = (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 + \dots) \quad (2)$$

It is possible to invert equation (1) to recover the original signal, s . The Moore-Penrose inverse [1] works well for this type of problem. This may be written functionally as

$$\begin{pmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ \vdots \\ s_n \end{pmatrix} = (D^\dagger D)^{-1} D^\dagger \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \vdots \\ y_m \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

This representation is useful since it effectively uses all the information buried in y to recover the original signal s . The key to the success of this inverse operation is getting an accurate representation of the time delays.

TIME-SHIFT OPERATORS

Time-shift operators are essential to this approach and can be constructed from matrices. It is useful to write the unit time-shift operator as

$$\Delta(1) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

This operator has the effect of shifting a time series vector forward by one unit.

$$a(n+1) = \Delta(1) a(n) \quad (5)$$

The measurement time, m , needs to be longer than the signal duration time, n . This is necessary to account for the various propagation delays. The resulting general $m \times n$ time-shift operators are then given by

$$\Delta(\tau) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & & & & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & & \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & & \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The delay parameter, τ , in this example is equal to an integer number of lags, which correspond to the number of zeros above the 1 in the first column. Delays should have a negative sign to be consistent with (4) and (5).

FRACTIONAL TIME-SHIFT OPERATORS

It is often necessary to include the more general case of fractional time shifts [2], [3]. Fractional in the sense that the time shift is a fraction of a time sample or lag. An example of the fractional time-shift operation is indicated below. In this case the time series vector is shifted by an arbitrary amount, τ .

$$a(n + \tau) = \Delta(\tau) a(n) \quad (7)$$

Construction of the fractional time-shift operator, $\Delta(\tau)$, for an arbitrary time shift, τ , is best done in the frequency domain. This representation can be accomplished by multiplying three matrices; the Fourier matrix, \mathcal{F} , the phase shift matrix, $\Delta(\theta)$, and the inverse Fourier matrix, \mathcal{F}^{-1} . This time-shift operator can be functionally written as

$$\Delta(\tau) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \Delta(\theta) \mathcal{F} \quad (8)$$

Multiplication of these matrices yields the following exact analytical expression for the fractional time-shift operator

$$\Delta(\tau) = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta_0 & \Delta_1 & \Delta_2 & \cdots & \Delta_{N-1} \\ \Delta_{-1} & \Delta_0 & \Delta_1 & \cdots & \Delta_{N-2} \\ \Delta_{-2} & \Delta_{-1} & \Delta_0 & \cdots & \Delta_{N-3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Delta_{-(N-1)} & \Delta_{-(N-2)} & \Delta_{-(N-3)} & \cdots & \Delta_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

This matrix has a Toeplitz structure. The diagonal terms, Δ_m , [not to be confused with the operators in (2)] are summations of geometric series and can be written as

$$\Delta_m = \frac{1}{N} \frac{1 - e^{2\pi i \tau}}{1 - e^{-2\pi i(m-\tau)/N}} \quad (10)$$

The analytical representation of the fractional time-shift operator is exact in a Fourier transform sense. This matrix operator is useful for precise interpolation of function values between sampled points.

A simple example of the fractional time shift (7) is shown in Fig. 1. The original signal (solid line) is shifted by $\tau = -0.5$ to produce the signal represented by small pluses. The sample rate is 2.5 times the signal frequency. The original samples are shown with circles and the time-shifted samples are shown with squares. This time-shift transformation exactly reproduces the shifted signal.

For large N equation (10) tends to have most diagonal terms that are near zero except for the m terms that are near τ . This is due to the overall $1/N$ factor and exponential term in the denominator. When m is near τ , the exponential term approaches one resulting in the denominator approaching zero. These terms then become significant. In practical applications this matrix can be approximated by using a sparse matrix containing only the dominant diagonals.

Fig. 1. Example of measured original signal (circles) and signal time-shifted by $\tau = -0.5$ (squares).

In practical situations it is necessary to pad the matrix, $\Delta(\tau)$, with rows of zeros at the top and bottom to account for the longer measurement time compared to the signal duration.

TIME DELAY ESTIMATION

Accurate estimates of the time delays of the signals are important. An optimal approach to this type of problem is the least-squares method. The metric or likelihood function to be minimized may be written as the difference between the measured data, y , and the parametric model, Ds .

$$L = \|y - Ds\|^2 \quad (11)$$

Inserting the Moore-Penrose inverse representation for s into equation (11) yields

$$L = y^\dagger y - y^\dagger D(D^\dagger D)^{-1} D^\dagger y \quad (12)$$

It is usually convenient to drop the constant term $y^\dagger y$ and flip the sign to yield a maximization problem.

$$L = y^\dagger D(D^\dagger D)^{-1} D^\dagger y \quad (13)$$

The product $D^\dagger D$ is simply the identity matrix when there is only one signal or when the signals do not overlap in time. In these cases the time shift operator is a unitary-like operator. The likelihood function can then be simply written as

$$L = \|D^\dagger y\|^2 \quad (14)$$

However, if the signals do overlap in time, then the problem requires the full representation given in (13). In this case the off-diagonal terms in $(D^\dagger D)^{-1}$ are important to account for the interference between the signals.

For completeness it should be mentioned that the likelihood function can also be expressed using a projection operator and a sample covariance matrix representation. Taking the trace of

equation (13) and rotating the vector y^\dagger to the right side of the equation yields

$$L = \text{tr}(D(D^\dagger D)^{-1} D^\dagger y y^\dagger) \quad (15)$$

$$= \text{tr}(D(D^\dagger D)^{-1} D^\dagger R).$$

This representation of the likelihood function is often seen in the literature and may or may not be computationally more efficient than (13).

To illustrate the utility of this time delay estimation approach an example is given. This example considers two overlapping chirp signals with length 100 time samples. The first signal arrives after a 50 time sample delay, and the second signal arrives after a 96 time sample delay. The measured time interval is 250 samples.

The likelihood function is numerically evaluated over a two dimensional grid for all values of the two time delays within ten time samples of the actual values. This result is shown in Fig. 2, and the original measured signal is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Time delay likelihood function for two chirp signals with peak at time delays of 50 lags and 96 lags.

Four things should be noted from this figure. First, the maximum of the likelihood function occurs at time delays of 50 and 96. These delays correspond to the best time delay estimates. Some noise was introduced into this calculation. This least-squares method was purposely developed to obtain the best estimates from noisy measurements.

It can also be seen that there are a number of local maximum and minimum in this figure. This can be traced back to the oscillatory nature of the original waveform. Any algorithm used to find the global maximum will have to account for this behavior.

It is somewhat interesting that the actual shape of the maximum is elongated along the diagonal direction. This indicates that the relative difference between the two time delays is strongly determined, and the estimates for the individual delays are less strongly determined.

It may be required that a more accurate estimates are needed than can be provided by a grid search at discrete time delays. One approach is to use fractional time-shift values and efficient search routines in the neighborhood of the global maximum. It might also be possible to achieve the desired accuracy by using a quadratic interpolation routine near the maximum of the likelihood function.

MULTIPATH CANCELLATION

Once the time delays are estimated it is possible to reconstruct the original waveform from the multiple measured waveforms using equation (3). An example of this technique with two chirp signals is shown in Fig. 3. The chirp signals are identical to the previous section example and have a length of 100 time samples and arrive at overlapping time delays of 50 and 96. The original chirp signal is recovered using the Moore-Penrose inverse and is shown below.

Fig. 3. Measured and recovered signals for two chirp signals.

Fig. 4. Measured and recovered signals for three chirp signals.

Fig. 4 shows another example of this technique with three chirp signals. The chirp signals are identical to the previous section example and have a length of 100 time samples and arrive at overlapping time delays of 50, 96 and 127. The original chirp signal is again recovered using the Moore-Penrose inverse.

TRUE SPECTRUM

Multipath environments make it difficult to obtain a true spectrum. The main problem is that the time delayed signals result in phase shifts in the frequency domain. Therefore, when the direct signal is combined with the time delayed multipath signals in the frequency domain, the phase shifts will tend to sum incoherently and reduce the frequency amplitudes. However, by reconstructing the original signal a true spectrum can be obtained. Fig. 5 shows an example with the same three chirp signals seen in Fig. 4. It should not be a surprise that the measured spectrum from the three multipath signals bears little resemblance to the true spectrum.

Fig. 5. Fourier spectra for measured and recovered signals for three chirp signal example.

COMMENTS

- *Signal retrieval in a multipath environment is a difficult and important challenge* in a large number of sensing and communication applications.
- *This paper uses a novel time domain approach to effectively cancel the multipath signals.* The key to this approach is to represent the problem using time shift matrix operators. Then the Moore-Penrose inverse can be used to recover the original signal.
- *Time delay estimation is critical to construct accurate time shift operators.* A likelihood function can be used to accurately estimate the time delays.
- *Various examples with broadband signals are shown.* It should be noted that a complementary paper in this conference uses a novel broadband steering vector to cancel these signals in the spatial domain [4].
- *Some further work is required to extend this time domain method to more applications.*

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